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Lessons for malaria elimination from the eradication of smallpox

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Lessons for malaria elimination from the eradication of smallpox

Justin M. Cohen

Abstract

Background. Malaria elimination and eventual eradication will require internationally coordinated approaches, high degrees of engagement from politicians and communities, efficient organizational structures, and well-managed programs. As governments and the global malaria community seek to overcome the associated challenges, their efforts should be informed by the substantial past experiences of other disease elimination and eradication programs, including that of the only successful eradication program of a human pathogen to date: smallpox.

Methods. A review of smallpox literature was conducted to identify lessons for malaria on how support for the undertaking was fostered internationally and domestically, how the campaign was internationally coordinated and financed, what programmatic strategies were found to be most successful, and how national elimination programs were most effectively structured and managed.

Results. Review of 118 publications related to the experience of smallpox suggests malaria eradication can succeed as a collection of individual country programs each deriving local solutions to local problems, yet with an important role for WHO and other international entities to facilitate and coordinate these efforts. Reflections on the smallpox experience suggest the importance of avoiding burdensome bureaucracy while employing flexible, problem-solving staff with both technical and operational backgrounds to nimbly overcome the numerous challenges that arise in an elimination program. Smallpox's hybrid program strategy that both leveraged basic health services while maintaining certain separate functions to maintain visibility, clear targets, and strong management aligns with current malaria approaches. Smallpox elimination succeeded in challenging settings by employing data-driven strategies that targeted resources to the places where they are most needed rather than attempting to achieve mass coverage everywhere, a potentially useful lesson for malaria programs seeking universal coverage with available tools. Finally, smallpox suggests strong engagement with the private sector and affected communities can help increase the sustainability and reach of today's malaria programs.

Conclusions. It remains unclear whether malaria eradication is feasible, but neither was it clear whether smallpox eradication was feasible until it was achieved. To increase chances of success, malaria programs should seek to strengthen program management, measurement, and operations, while building flexible means of sharing experiences, tools, and financing internationally.

Keywords: malaria, eradication, elimination, smallpox, history

Background

The World Health Organization (WHO) has called for the eradication of malaria since 1955 [1], and although the 1969 World Health Assembly "re-examined" that goal [2], it was never officially abandoned. Today, the WHO's Global Technical Strategy [3] calls for gradual process towards

eradication with at least 10 new countries eliminating malaria by 2020, 10 more by 2025, and another 15 by 2030. Achieving these targets with the imperfect, impermanent tools available to malaria elimination programs will require internationally coordinated approaches, high degrees of engagement from politicians and communities, efficient organizational structures, and well-managed programs. As governments and the global malaria community seek to overcome the associated challenges, their efforts should be informed by the substantial past experiences of other disease elimination and eradication programs.

Smallpox is the only infectious disease of humans to have been eradicated globally. Donald A. Henderson, the director of WHO's successful smallpox eradication campaign from 1966-1977, was skeptical about malaria eradication, stating that it was not feasible with currently available tools [4], and that even with a high quality vaccine, smallpox eradication "proved to be infinitely more difficult than I or anyone else had imagined it would be" [5]. Given that the WHO continues to view eradication as the ultimate goal of control efforts, however, it is worth examining the smallpox eradication experience to understand what lessons can be learned about how to approach such an ambitious undertaking.

Drawing lessons for malaria from the smallpox program is inherently challenging due to the different interventions (i.e., a highly protective, long-lasting vaccine for smallpox versus imperfect anti-vector and parasite tools for malaria that must be repeatedly re-distributed) and disease dynamics. Yet it is plausible to expect there are also political, operational, financial, and administrative commonalities to any global undertaking of this nature. The need to coordinate across so many stakeholders across so many endemic countries, to finance a many year enterprise, and to ensure countries act in concert to minimize importation from neighbors means the malaria community will be "forced to navigate complex administrative and societal terrains, where knowledge gleaned from scientific and medical journals can only be partially useful" [6], but where past experiences managing similar programs may prove valuable.

Methods

To investigate potential lessons for malaria in the smallpox literature, PubMed was searched on 7 Feb 2017 for "smallpox" and "eradication" in the title or abstract of publications. Seven hundred results were returned. Abstracts were evaluated to assess whether the publication would provide information about seven areas of interest, selected in collaboration with members of WHO's Strategic Advisory Group on Malaria Eradication. These areas included the international themes of (1) how support for the undertaking was fostered internationally, (2) how the campaign was internationally coordinated, and (3) how it was financed. At a national level, themes included (4) how support was fostered nationally and (5) at community level, (6) what programmatic strategies were found to be most successful, and (7) how national elimination programs were most effectively structured and managed. Additional references cited in the PubMed results that seemed relevant, including several books, were also included in review.

Abstracts of all results were examined for relevance to one of these seven areas of interest. The full texts of all relevant publications were read by the author, who noted any lessons relevant to the operational, political, and financial challenges of malaria eradication. These ramifications for malaria were collated and summarized.

Results

Of 700 results returned by the PubMed search, 118 publications were selected for full-text review. These documents, which ranged in publication year from 1959 to 2015, included contemporary accounts of the campaign from specific countries, assessments of global program process, and reflections on the eradication accomplishment by its participants in both journal article and book form, along with several reviews of the smallpox experience. A number of themes emerge from the literature across the seven areas of interest (Table 1).

International support for the eradication program

Henderson declared, “For a global programme against a disease to be undertaken, universal political commitment is necessary” [7]. In the case of malaria, support for fighting the disease is strong, with malaria control activities frequently cited as one of the “best buys in global health” [8–10]. However, the pursuit of malaria eradication is more controversial, and whether it represents a feasible or even a worthwhile goal has been frequently debated [11–18].

Support for the smallpox eradication program was similarly far from universal. The failures of prior eradication or regional elimination efforts including hookworm, malaria, yellow fever, and yaws increased skepticism, as did a perception that vertical eradication campaigns detracted from provision of basic health services [5]. Although WHO was tasked with coordinating the effort from Geneva, its diverse departments and regional offices were not uniformly behind the effort, in part because “their officials competed with each other for finite financial resources and administrative influence” [19]. The Director-General of WHO reportedly had so little faith in the program that he explained to Henderson – a secondee from the United States Centers for Disease Control (CDC) – that “he wanted an American as the director so that when the programme failed, as he was sure it would, the Americans, not WHO, would be seen as responsible” [20].

The smallpox program survived at WHO in part because of strong backing from both the United States and the USSR [20], the major powers of the era. Henderson himself was seen as a trustworthy leader by both rival countries despite ongoing Cold War hostilities because of his strong track record as an “honest and a good scientist” whose “only objective [was] to eradicate smallpox” [20]. Still, maintaining smallpox’s profile within WHO and encouraging countries to contribute funding and resources was an ongoing challenge. Henderson used the annual meeting of the WHO assembly as an important opportunity to keep eradication on the minds of health ministers [4] and tried to maintain smallpox’s public profile by widely releasing surveillance reports with summaries of progress and problems. Henderson later suggested that a mistake he made was not adding dedicated staff to his team focused on public relations and donor advocacy [7]. Malaria today appears to have a more visible profile internationally than smallpox did, in part due to similar communications efforts, such as the annual World Malaria Report which provides opportunities for visibility and public engagement [21].

International coordination of the eradication program

International coordination was considered important to avoid “ping-pong smallpox” [22] in which infections would be continually reintroduced from country to country. A 1960 Inter-Regional Smallpox Conference organized by WHO reported that since “the eradication of smallpox cannot be considered on the basis of individual territories,” the Conference “therefore urges the health administrations of all countries in endemic regions to synchronize their eradication campaigns” [23]. While this declaration was sufficient to spur action in some countries [24], others, including Brazil – the country with the largest burden in the Americas – and many African countries [25] declined to initiate vaccination programs, compromising the possibility of regional success [26]. Provision of dedicated smallpox funding in 1967 proved critical to allow WHO to incentivize countries to scale up their national programs [7], even when committed funding was small [26]. There is little doubt that the provision of donor funding for malaria – increasing from about \$170 million in 2000 to \$2.5 billion in 2016 [27] – has been similarly important to convince countries to prioritize malaria programming.

Despite the international push from WHO, the smallpox eradication effort would always remain a collection of individual national programs, each attempting to solve their own problems through their own systems and in their own ways [25], rather than a top-down, centrally managed global undertaking. William Foege called it “20 programs trying different things to more quickly discover truth” [28].

“The campaign to eradicate smallpox worldwide is often described in simplistic terms... The picture presented is of a unitary programme of action, where the many cogs in the wheel apparently worked in almost perfect harmony, causing orders from the top of an administrative pyramid to be unquestioningly implemented in localities across the globe... the organized drive to expunge smallpox was a much more complicated and disjointed entity.” [29]

Current malaria guidance embraces an aligned belief that “adapting and tailoring interventions” to the local context will be important for elimination success [30]. Despite the importance of local solutions, WHO and other international entities including the US CDC [31] added substantial value to these independent programs, including:

- 1) *Sharing best practices across countries.* WHO’s guidance to countries evolved substantially over the course of the program as understanding of what worked and what didn’t evolved. Its initial recommendation for every country to vaccinate at least 80% of the population increased to a goal of 100% vaccination [25], before being replaced with a dramatically different recommendation to invest heavily in surveillance and to focus vaccination on the places where transmission was observed. Well after several programs had successfully eliminated smallpox by shifting from mass vaccination of the entire population to much more efficient and effective surveillance-driven targeted approaches, many countries resisted this change [32]. WHO’s leadership in pushing for adoption of proven approaches across additional countries was thus critical [33].
- 2) *Ensuring the quality of tools.* The vaccination campaign relied upon having a stable, reliable, effective vaccine [34]. Yet when the newly established eradication headquarters in WHO established a system for testing batches of vaccine produced in more than 40 different countries, it found <10% of samples were acceptable [35] due to potency and heat stability

issues [36]. WHO engaged vaccine experts to write simple manuals of production that explained best available production methods [37], and WHO consultants worked with laboratories to improve their production processes [37]. Local production of vaccine was set up in the largest population countries including Brazil, India, and Indonesia, since donations would otherwise have been insufficient [37]. Two high quality laboratories from the Netherlands and Canada were selected to serve as vaccine reference centers [34], and they performed batch testing to evaluate improvements. As a result of these efforts, the fraction of batches meeting quality standards rose to 31% in 1967, 76% in 1972, and 96% in 1976 [33]. WHO today provides a quality control function for malaria commodities, prequalifying malaria drugs and pesticides, and evaluating performance of rapid tests [38], though it is less directly involved in commodity production. The smallpox experience suggests that investment in the production of bed-nets in high-volume countries could be considered as a possible means of reducing reliance on imported, donor-funded products [39].

- 3) *Provision of technical and operational support.* WHO's smallpox eradication unit provided both field epidemiologists and administrators to help manage logistics to national programs. Over the 12 years of the program, 687 different individuals from 73 countries participated in the WHO-sponsored program [40]. The expansion of WHO's role from solely providing technical advice to actively enabling operations was a learning experience for the Geneva-based program [41]. But this evolution allowed Geneva to strengthen global logistics, moving supplies from one country to another as needed, or flexibly providing necessary funds to overcome bottlenecks [7]. It was noted that WHO was most effective when its staff, including senior leadership spent their time working in country with programs [42]. Henderson stated his opinion that the most effective WHO staff "were those who took an active role in field operations. Those who assumed a passive role of detached technical adviser were encouraged to leave the programme" [7]. Similar sorts of temporary field advisors have been deployed under the STOP-Polio program [43] and can prove useful for building capacity in malaria programs if deployed thoughtfully [44].

In playing these roles, there was agreement that WHO's success was strongly linked to the ability to be as flexible and non-bureaucratic as possible [18]. Sometimes, as when flying to countries with outbreaks without receiving travel approvals, this meant breaking WHO rules [36], something Henderson deemed necessary given "a sclerotic... administration that often thwarted or actively impeded what appeared to be logical initiatives" [5]. In one example, an emergency request for vaccine supply from Uganda took five months to be transmitted to headquarters by the regional WHO office, during which time the Geneva office had already learned about the outbreak and addressed it via informal backchannels [4]. Internal WHO disagreements also led to challenges, with Henderson noting that, "Officials located within different levels and departments of the regional offices continued to hold disparate views right till global smallpox eradication was formally certified" [29]. He complained that, "The regional offices of WHO... were more a hindrance than a help," leading Henderson to adopt a "policy of quietly short-circuiting the regional office, when necessary" [4].

The challenge for a complex bureaucracy like WHO to move beyond technical advice to actively enabling operational response have been echoed in recent years by criticism surrounding its response the 2013-

2016 Ebola outbreak in West Africa [45,46]. The success of WHO's smallpox team may provide a model for how a Geneva-based team can nimbly and flexibly facilitate malaria operations across endemic countries. However, the fact that Henderson and colleagues viewed their success as something they achieved despite WHO's structures and procedures – for example, by creating a new unit within a regional office that reported directly to Henderson rather than through the normal channels [29] – rather than because of them, suggests that consideration will need to be given to how to ensure a central malaria coordination team is encouraged and enabled to be agile and flexible, as is required by the rapidly evolving nature of a global eradication enterprise.

Financing the program

The financial argument for malaria elimination typically assumes that a substantial short term budget increase will be required to achieve elimination, after which long term savings can be realized due to a lower cost program to prevent re-establishment of transmission [47]. Surprisingly, in the case of smallpox, Henderson argues no such surge in funding was required, with existing domestic budgets covering the majority of elimination needs:

“The burden of expenditure has been borne by the endemic countries themselves... But, with few exceptions, the expenditure by the countries has been little more than what they were already spending to *control* smallpox. In other words, WHO and its member countries, with only a very modest additional input in resources, have transformed a neverending control programme to a successful *eradication* programme.” [26]

The idea that smallpox could be eliminated from countries with essentially the same budget previously used to control it is remarkable, and suggests that how funds were spent proved far more critical than the total amount of those funds. As Henderson describes:

“For all of us it has been a revelation in so many countries to find at the periphery such an array of unproductive health staff and facilities. It has been a revelation to discover how effectively they may be mobilized with a comparatively small input involving leadership in the field and definition of a series of activities with defined objectives and a modest element of management. Other health programmes, especially those involving immunization, but others as well, could, I believe, be similarly transformed.” [26]

The importance of using available funding better was an international issue as well as a national one. WHO internal dynamics and disagreements between regional offices complicated the efficient expenditure of available funding. In the Americas, for example, PAHO at one point chose to distribute available funding across the entire region, even though Brazil was the only remaining endemic country [48]. As a result, Brazil's funding was insufficient and elimination programs were prolonged unnecessarily [11]. SEARO chose to pass up the available funding rather than participate in the program, which it disagreed with; Henderson then channeled the money to PAHO in hopes it would be spent in Brazil. When five years later Brazil was finally free of smallpox, PAHO refused to donate its funds back to SEARO in turn to assist India [4].

It is unclear if Henderson's comparison of the costs for control versus eradication factored in the 407 million doses of vaccine that were donated over the course of the program, primarily by the Soviet Union and the United States [26], at an average estimated value of \$17 per 1,000 [48]. In total, \$67 million in cash and kind (including vaccine) was donated to the WHO's special account for smallpox eradication between 1967-1979, while \$33.6 million was spent from WHO's regular budget [48]. This total of approximately \$7.7M per year would translate to around \$30-\$50 million in today's dollars – far less than the \$2B per year currently contributed by international donors to malaria programs [49].

The argument made to donors to secure these funds was that “all should be willing to contribute to carry the attack to the remaining endemic regions until there is no more smallpox” [50]. The United States, for example, was said to be domestically spending \$140M annually in 1968 to keep out smallpox domestically, and thus its modest investment of \$15M to eliminate in West and Central Africa meant that it could help 20 countries become smallpox free for the price of 39 days of preventing its reintroduction back home [31]. A similar argument was used to successfully convince the Swedish government to make a critical contribution to the program in India, since “every country is in danger until the last case of smallpox has been eliminated” [19].

The availability of even small amounts of funding that could be used flexibly, with minimal bureaucracy, was seen as critical to bypassing bottlenecks. “It was essential to have an allocation of funds that could be used for any necessary purpose and in any country” [7], yet nearly all available funds for smallpox eradication were earmarked for specific uses. As a result, staff were often not paid on time, insufficient gas allowances meant vehicles were not available when needed, and funding for car repairs was lacking in multiple countries [7]. In Zaire, for example, operations would frequently grind to a halt after the government would fail to release the necessary funds; the program solved the issue by setting up an auxiliary bank account in which they deposited back-up funds whenever possible to cover expenditure during these gap periods [4]. In Bihar, India, “staff were fearful of paying too much [for vehicle maintenance] and being held accountable for extra charges” [41], so vehicles were often neglected instead. New accounts were set up to give team leads advances for these minor but essential charges so that they could avoid weeks of paperwork to receive necessary funds, instead providing receipts at subsequent meetings on a biweekly or monthly basis. This approach dramatically improved the flexibility of the elimination efforts and Henderson deemed it “one of the most important initiatives of the program” [4].

Malaria programs today frequently experience similar delays due to challenges with financial expenditure. Many countries have failed to spend Global Fund grants on schedule due to a wide variety of challenges, including lack of human resources, delays in procurement, weak data systems, and other challenges [51]. The smallpox experience suggests that the proactive creation of a flexible fund that could be used to address bottlenecks across countries as they arise could be a valuable tool for malaria as eradication proceeds. It also emphasizes the critical importance of having strong measurement and management of programs to ensure available funds are allocated and used as effectively as possible.

Domestic support for the program

Political will has been cited as one of the most important factors in the success of smallpox eradication [11] and a necessity for eliminating malaria [30]. Not all countries viewed smallpox elimination as an urgent priority given many other public health issues [25], just as malaria elimination is often a low priority today for countries facing more visible threats [52]. Competing disease priorities, including ongoing malaria eradication efforts [26], led governments such as that of Ethiopia to have “absolutely no interest in the eradication of smallpox” [53]. Non-governmental actors such as UNICEF also had prior commitments to malaria eradication that took precedence over contributions to smallpox [4].

Countries where the less virulent variola minor predominated over the far more deadly variola major, mostly in Africa, tended to downplay the importance of embarking on an elimination program, given that this strain of the disease was “little more serious than chicken pox” [4]. Henderson cited this reticence as one of the two primary factors compromising the young program (the other being the absence of funding) [7]. This challenge is echoed by questions of whether malaria eradication should aim to include all species of the disease or only (or initially) the more virulent *Plasmodium falciparum* given its outsized contribution to mortality as well as its development or resistance to artemisinin-based drugs in the Greater Mekong subregion. The smallpox experience does not answer the question of whether an effort to only eradicate variola major could have succeeded (and thus whether a *P. falciparum*-only attempted could be feasible), though the similarity of symptoms between the two would have complicated case finding directed only at the major variant.

Political backing also suffered with changes in government and thus the loss of advocates: “Within four years after the West African program began, there were 23 changes of governments in the 18 participating countries,” leading to changing leadership and staff in the nation's smallpox program” [54]. In India, it was noted that the Prime Minister’s enthusiasm for smallpox typically increased when outbreaks were observed – and thus when the electorate was most concerned about the disease – and declined with smallpox incidence [19]. Pressure from powerful allies outside the government was thus seen as critical to ensure the program remained sufficiently well supported even when smallpox was not in the headlines. An agreement to begin a vaccination program in Ethiopia only occurred due to the intercession of a senior Austrian physician with a close relationship with the Emperor [53], while in India, the intercession of J.R.D. Tata, the well-connected head of a large corporation, played a critical role in convincing the Prime Minister to continue supporting the smallpox program at a pivotal moment [19]. In Bhutan, where the WHO initially lacked visibility into smallpox efforts due to the secrecy of its government, an acquaintance of Henderson’s with access to the royal family was eventually able to build communications with Geneva [55].

A lesson for malaria is thus the importance of getting well-connected leaders from business and high-profile institutions to act as advocates. The opinion of politicians can change based on what seems important for the next election, but these examples show how they can be convinced based in counsel from those they trust or respect. Malaria appears to already be doing a better job of identifying high-profile advocates than smallpox ever did. Organizations with the explicit goal of maintaining malaria’s global or regional visibility, such as Malaria No More or the African Leaders Malaria Alliance, identify champions who can contribute funding and political backing to national efforts [56], while the Bill and

Melinda Gates Foundation-led End Malaria Council seeks to bring business leaders together with public sector leaders to keep malaria a global priority.

Community support for the program

Community participation with the smallpox program was considered generally strong [4], although the literature contains numerous accounts of specific anecdotes of resistance to vaccination particularly following real or perceived adverse reactions to the vaccine [25]. Some commentators note that the narrow focus on smallpox was sometimes counterproductive given the range of health issues afflicting communities. In Bangladesh, for example, vaccination occurred in the midst of a cholera epidemic, yet the vaccinators could provide no assistance with the more visible and urgent problem, resulting in community frustration [57]. As the program proceeded, additional components were therefore added onto the responsibilities of surveillance agents to keep them engaged and motivated despite the infrequency with which smallpox was observed, including surveys investigating access to clean water, Vitamin A, family planning, and rates of childhood mortality [57]. Similarly, malaria-only village workers may prove less successful than those that have been trained to treat a variety of common illnesses [58].

Gaining the support of community leaders was commonly cited as a crucial step towards community acceptance. In Nigeria, Foege believed that people participated less because they were convinced by vaccinators to do so and more because they trusted their leaders [32]. In one extraordinary case, vaccinators were reported to have awed a village chief into supporting the program by releasing a trained bird to swoop overhead and drop pro-vaccine leaflets while vaccinators were meeting with him [26]. Despite such anecdotes, Tarantola and Foster note that little research was conducted into how the community could best be engaged [57], though attempts to do so included deployment of midwives and other village workers to engage and educate the community [34,59] as well as provision of monetary awards for report of a smallpox case in the final stages of the program [60]. In India, for example, a 100 rupee reward was offered for anyone reporting a previously unknown outbreak [26]. The evidence base for what drives patient participation with the health system has increased in subsequent decades, identifying factors related to cost, proximity, and confidence [61], but the relative ability of different interventions to influence those factors likely still requires additional research. Best practices for proactive engagement of community leaders and ongoing communication and collaboration with at-risk populations should be encouraged to make communities active participants in malaria elimination programs [62].

Where efforts to improve participation failed, smallpox programs would sometimes use compulsory vaccination, an approach that dispensed with “the need to converse with villagers at all” [63]. Compulsory vaccination was believed to be justified by the need to achieve sufficient coverage for the greater good, but raises troubling ethical questions. Greenough quotes Stanley Music, an epidemiologist who worked in the Bangladesh program, on the tactics sometimes employed:

“In the hit-and-run excitement of such a campaign, women and children were often pulled out from under beds, from behind doors, from within latrines, etc... Attempts were made to secure the cooperation and ‘blessing’ of village headmen, thereby putting social pressure on the

villagers to stand their ground and accept vaccination. Still, however, some form of minor chaos was the rule, as headmen's authority did not extend into individual's homes... People were chased and, when caught, vaccinated... We went from door to door and vaccinated. When they ran, we chased. When they locked their doors, we broke down their doors and vaccinated them." [63]

While these aggressive approaches did in some cases attain the narrow goal of achieving high vaccination coverage, they seem unwise for a program such as malaria in which long-term participation and repeated delivery cycles is needed. Ethically, they were controversial even at the time, and "the organized and sustained use of compulsion was, generally speaking, instituted with great care and only after broad administrative and political consensus had been achieved" [19].

Engagement with the private sector was reported to be generally minimal outside a few efforts to integrate private health care providers into the vaccination program [57]. India proved one of the main exceptions, with the Tata Group playing a critical role in vaccinating the population of Bihar State, where its steel plant was located. They provided "medical and paramedical personnel, transportation, managerial support and communication facilities to implement the programme activities. The assistance in kind provided by the Company and their local knowledge of the area were so valuable that south Bihar became smallpox-free in a record period of 6 months" [64]. Malaria's recent history includes several examples of similar partnerships [65].

Programmatic strategy

Smallpox eradication was predicated on the idea of mass vaccination of the population. The WHO's Expert Committee initially called for countries to achieve at least 80% vaccination of the population [26]. This approach successfully led to elimination in some countries, but elsewhere it failed, likely because the vaccinated and unvaccinated fractions of the population were not homogeneously mixed [33]. In Central Java, for example, a 1969 survey found greater than 95% vaccination rates had been achieved across the population of 23 million people, yet that same year over 1,700 cases were recorded, nearly all amongst the 5% of the population who had been missed [66]. The WHO Expert Committee responded by telling countries they should strive for 100% vaccination rates, a target scorned as impossible [26]. Attempts to conduct greater numbers of vaccinations were undertaken, but "accessible groups, like schoolchildren, were vaccinated repeatedly so that high 'scores' were achieved, but there always remained a large pool of unvaccinated persons" [42]. This language is mirrored in a recent investigation of bed net coverage across Africa by Bhatt et al., which concluded:

"We found substantial over-allocation of nets to households already owning a sufficient quantity... What is certain is that over-allocation becomes a major barrier to achieving universal coverage when levels of ITN provision are high because most new incoming nets are simply leading to surpluses in many households, while elsewhere there remains a shortfall. This may have a disproportionately high public health impact if those surplus nets are concentrated in households at lowest risk." [67]

The critical change in smallpox programs was a shift away from mass vaccination towards an approach called “surveillance-containment” [31] in which programs sought out smallpox cases and then concentrated vaccination efforts in those areas and towards those who may have come into contact with the cases. In short, the new strategy meant focusing vaccination on the places where it was most likely to matter, rather than laboring to achieve implausibly perfect coverage everywhere. In Bangladesh, for example, the program successfully ended transmission after abandoning efforts to achieve 80% vaccination nationally and focusing efforts instead only on the northern districts where cases were reported [36].

The 1964 WHO Expert Committee report did not even mention surveillance [4], but the new focus on finding cases, tracking down all of their contacts, and concentrating vaccination operations in the most necessary places was considered by many to be one of the keys to eradication’s ultimate success [11,68]. Identifying where smallpox was being transmitted required a network of agents who visited all health units to ensure weekly reporting and sought out cases via the community, such as by working with teachers or visiting markets [66]. Case finding was intensified particularly during the period of lowest seasonal incidence, since that low transmission season represented the weakest point in the smallpox cycle and the best opportunity to break transmission, despite the operational challenge of finding cases [69]. Active case finding was integrated with routine reporting from public health facilities, rather than building an entirely parallel apparatus [70]. A surveillance team of 2-4 people per administrative unit would follow up with facilities to ensure good reporting, as well as to distribute surveillance reports so that the health staff saw how their reports were being used [70]. “Undoubtedly, the greatest stimulus to reporting was the prompt visit of the surveillance team for outbreak investigations and control whenever cases were reported,” Henderson wrote. “This simple, obvious and direct indication that the routine weekly reports were actually seen and were a cause for public health action did more, I am sure, than the multitude of government directives which were issued” [70]. Challenges to setting up good surveillance systems included the fact that in many countries, disease reporting fell under the purview of independent statistical units and were not thus within the control of the smallpox program [7] (the same is true for malaria today in some countries).

It is important to note that the operational plan undertaken for smallpox is not directly translatable to malaria. First, the approach may have worked in part because the reproductive rate for the virus was relatively low [31], estimated at approximately 3.5 to 6 [71], while estimates for malaria are variable but potentially far higher [72]. Second, case finding was far easier because the symptoms of the disease were so distinctive and recognizable even to schoolchildren [70].

However, the critical shift in smallpox programs from judging success based on the volume of vaccinations to whether vaccination was achieved in the most necessary places still suggests a good model for malaria programs. Malaria programs that seek only to distribute commodities such as nets or drugs in high volumes in an attempt to achieve “universal” coverage may be missing more inaccessible populations which may also be the highest risk for malaria [67,73]; shifting towards a risk-focused approach in which prevention and treatment are targeted to those who most need them has great potential for improving the efficiency and effectiveness of our efforts.

National program structure and management

Discussion of the wisdom of eradication programs often revolves around the relative merits of “vertical,” single disease programs versus “horizontal” health systems efforts [11], which were increasingly coming into favor at WHO around the time of smallpox eradication. Henderson advocated for having a specific vaccination program distinct from, yet linked to, routine health services, worrying that fully integrated programs would lack clear objectives, evaluation systems, and management structures. “The ‘horizontal programs’ I have seen best describe the sleeping postures of the workers” [68], he wrote. In contrast he considered a “targeted and time-limited special programme with funds specially allocated for it, both in the WHO budget and in most national budgets, and with full-time technical staff responsible for its supervision” [7] to be superior since it would more easily attract resources and community support and be more efficient and better managed than if it was one of many health programs. Such programs were also viewed as attractive because they could be conducted even while basic health services remained weak [50]. The vertical versus horizontal health program debate has persisted since smallpox [74] and will not be resolved here, yet a few clear lessons for malaria emerge from smallpox’s successes.

First, smallpox programs were well integrated with basic health systems, enabling routine case management and surveillance, with active case finding used as a supplement rather than a replacement. This integrated design improved upon the design of the Global Malaria Eradication Program preceding it in the 1950s and 1960s, which largely elided basic health systems. The malaria eradication program measured malaria primarily via population prevalence surveys [75] and other active means [76] and conducted insecticide spray campaigns as vertical efforts. Malaria staff were also better paid than other workers and reported to heads of state rather than ministries of health, creating unsustainable systems [5]. In contrast, smallpox programs were still part of the health system, leveraging the same basic health services and staff to identify and report the disease [7,29]. This integration meant that smallpox teams were not required to set up fully parallel surveillance systems, instead augmenting existing ones and leaving behind some added capacity within health programs. Reliance upon the routine, albeit imperfect, measurement of malaria that basic health systems provide across endemic regions seems likely to greatly improve the cost-effectiveness of surveillance given that it requires no expenditure required beyond keeping health facilities stocked with diagnostic tests, training staff in their use, and linking them to effective reporting systems. Such investment such core case management systems is a primary component of WHO’s Global Technical Strategy for malaria [3].

Second, multiple authors highlighted the importance of creative, problem-solving staff [28] who could figure out how to overcome any obstacle that arose, tailoring solutions to the unique challenges and contexts faced by each country [7]. Henderson described: “The essence of what has made the programme what it is is, very simply, an imaginative and dedicated field staff, both national and international, who, given scope and encouragement to work out problems according to local circumstances and support in their efforts to do so, have responded with some remarkable solutions to impossible problems” [26]. These resourceful workers, described by former United States Surgeon General Julius Richmond as “simply too young to know it couldn’t be done” [77], were supported by a similarly flexible international team at WHO, who were described as:

“Essentially problem-solvers, they viewed themselves as catalysts rather than as controllers. They understood from the onset that experimental learning offered the only possibility for success. They avoided formalized programming, opting instead for innovation, flexibility, communication and experiment, by means of a number of deliberate policies and mechanisms. They recruited people with practical field experience in epidemiology (as opposed to previous work with smallpox per se). They sought people with reputations for adaptability, imagination, and hard work. They preferred younger people, assuming they would be more receptive to new approaches and ideas.” [78] quoted in [34].

Henderson contrasted the flexibility with which smallpox programs worked with the unsuccessful prior malaria eradication effort, which he said “was conceived and executed as a military operation to be conducted in an identical manner whatever the battlefield” [79], preventing it from adapting to local contexts, structures, and systems.

Third, smallpox programs placed great emphasis on careful measurement and verification. “Logic suggests that all disease control programmes should provide continuous measurements of disease incidence, and that these measurements should dictate changes in strategy and tactics,” wrote Henderson. “In fact, few programmes do so. Responsible authorities tend to ignore such information or dismiss efforts to obtain the data and, instead, assess progress in terms of activity, such as the numbers of vaccinations performed or patients treated” [7]. Arguably, today’s malaria programs continue to focus more activities conducted rather than impact, given that primary metrics reported as proof of progress of grants from the Global Fund to Fight AIDS, Tuberculosis, and Malaria focus on the number of nets or drugs delivered, rather than specific reductions in outcome metrics. The smallpox experience suggests that successful elimination may require shifting focus from simply tallying how many commodities have been distributed towards assessment of whether those tools are being used as effectively as possible.

In West and Central Africa, smallpox programs used three different types of evaluation approaches: first, evaluators would follow-up to assess whether what vaccinators claimed to have done had truly been accomplished; second, tally sheet comparisons were made to compare vaccination records against any available census data, as a quick if somewhat inaccurate estimation of whether numbers were approximately what should be expected; third, spot checks for vaccine scars were conducted at markets and other convenient gathering places to provide an independent confirmation of coverage [80]. Henderson stressed that in measurement, quality was more important than quantity: “a few indicators of overall performance, closely followed, were more useful than a broad spectrum of indicators measuring many aspects of programme execution” [7].

How to build appropriate teams and processes to conduct this measurement and verification was determined on a country by country basis. In Bolivia, one inspector was appointed for every eight to 12 vaccinators, ensuring everyone’s work was reviewed at least biweekly [81]. In India, a Central Appraisal Team oversaw evaluation processes, including frequent travel to trouble spots to assess what was going wrong [4]. Ensuring accurate reporting was sometimes compromised when workers avoided reporting true cases because they thought they would be punished for allowing transmission in their region [59],

underscoring the importance of clear and frequent communication between central and local levels. “The best results were obtained where WHO, national, and state or provincial supervisory staff travelled frequently into the field to review activities and to work with field staff in resolving problems. Monthly or bimonthly meetings in which field staff and supervisors from different areas met to discuss progress and problems and to compare differences in results were also of value” [7]. Widespread distribution of smallpox indicators was encouraged, such as through surveillance bulletins in Brazil which were distributed on a monthly basis to a wide audience, providing updates on progress, putting pressure on non-reporters to participate, and generally helping to foster a shared sense of purpose across the diverse network of individuals participating in the campaign [4].

Fourth, the smallpox program emphasized the importance of strong management in all aspects of the program. Henderson suggests that, “Successful execution of the programme consists of perhaps 10% technical skill and 90% organization and leadership” [26]. He stressed the importance of leaders actually spending substantial time out in the villages where the work is being done, leading by example and helping motivate workers: “effective leadership to solve the problems faced by field workers cannot be supplied by an army of physicians and senior supervisors who never leave their desks. Regrettably, these types are all too plentiful throughout the world” [26]. These opinions were substantiated by an evaluation of unsuccessful programs in India, Pakistan, Argentina, Iran, and Ghana, which found that:

“First and most important, failure appeared to be associated with inadequate supervision and assessment. Programmes that failed normally showed the following shortcomings: (a) supervisory personnel did not check at the family level to assure that broad coverage by vaccination of the population was being achieved; (b) supervisors were too burdened by other responsibilities to give more than nominal supervision; (c) inadequate provisions for travel and expenses; and (d) disinclination of supervisors to undergo the inconvenience of field work.” [19]

William Foege described how “the real problems” of “developing routines, documenting the implementation of those routines, hiring the right people, supervising, motivating, and evaluating” required “managers, administrators, and logistics experts – people who knew how to solve problems and how to get things done. The program would not fail for lack of scientists, but it could fail – even with the best strategy – if we didn't attract the very best managers” [28]. Strong management was required to keep up staff enthusiasm for searching for smallpox when there was nothing left to find [19]; in one case, near the very end of the program in Ethiopia, a surveillance agent walked for 15 days to check on two reported cases which turned out to be chickenpox [26].

Programs accordingly sought to hire non-medical, logistics-oriented staff with experience in administration in addition to those with a more conventional public health background [69]. Once brought into the program, strong managers had to be retained: in Brazil, for example, five different directors were appointed in the five years between 1967-1971 [11] with unsurprisingly weak results. Henderson suggested that providing program leaders management training would have been a wise idea, though it was not done at the time [7].

Discussion

The successful eradication of smallpox holds many lessons for malaria eradication efforts, despite the considerable differences between the programs. Smallpox succeeded as a collection of individual country programs each deriving local solutions to local problems, yet with an important role for WHO and other international entities to facilitate and enable these efforts by ensuring the best possible tools were available, maintaining the disease's profile globally, fundraising, and arm-twisting in reluctant countries to ensure coordinated action. Smallpox's experience suggests that such coordinating efforts must be nimble and flexible to stay relevant to rapidly changing country situations, and burdensome bureaucracy must be avoided if international agencies such as WHO are to add value rather than increasing the challenge of disease elimination.

Smallpox leaders stress the importance of empowering countries to solve problems locally. Where a strategy or tool has been proven to work well, efficient mechanisms for sharing those experiences are essential. Yet each country will need to adapt those effective approaches given their diversity of populations, systems, strengths, and weaknesses. Global leadership must ensure countries are able to access the most effective tools available, and understand the best principles for how to use them, but the smallpox experience suggests there is no script to be followed in elimination, no simple set of checkboxes that if ticked will result in success. Countries did benefit from the provision of international technical advice and logistical support, helping build country capacity. The particular importance of administrative support to national programs suggests distinct cadres of staff can add substantial value to malaria elimination programs: people from public health backgrounds can help with technical aspects, but logistical people are needed to help plan and execute efficient operations. The smallpox experience also emphasizes the critical importance of hiring program leaders and managers who are enthusiastic about spending time with communities and local programs, and who are creative thinkers who can derive context-appropriate solutions to the challenging problems that will inevitably arise.

Smallpox eradication is reported not to have involved a substantial increase in domestic budgets, but rather was achieved by better managing programs and streamlining how they spent the available funds. A clear lesson is that data-driven approaches that target resources to the places where they are most needed will be more successful for elimination than mass attempts to achieve universal coverage everywhere; such a shift in mindset proved similarly successful in the eradication of rinderpest, with surveillance-targeted vaccination providing much more impactful than total coverage [82]. Minimizing inefficiencies in malaria programs to ensure available funds have the greatest possible impact should be a high priority. While the malaria community continues to advocate for increased funding from donors, spending available funding as efficiently as possible will be critical. In addition, the importance of flexible funding – even in small amounts – was repeatedly stressed. Setting up a central malaria account that can be rapidly and flexibly used for filling gaps and bypassing bottlenecks could be an important step towards enabling malaria eradication. Finally, means of reducing dependence on donor-funded commodities, such as investment in local manufacturing, may need to be considered.

Although government programs will lead the fight against malaria, the smallpox experience suggests affected communities and the private sector will have critical roles in facilitating the program. Building a malaria elimination program that is visible for fundraising and that has its own discrete, measurable milestones will drive programs to hold themselves accountable and focus on achieving results rather

than just distributing commodities. However, nesting those programs within basic health services is critical to leverage routine case management and reporting that malaria programs do not specifically have to pay for, increasing sustainability and the reach of the program.

An innate limitation of this review is that it depends upon the published literature, which is constrained by the availability of viewpoints of those who have published [55]. Smallpox was a global undertaking with diverse contributions of healthcare workers at all levels of international and national programs, yet accounts in the literature are primarily written by director-level staff from the United States and Europe. Accordingly, this review is biased substantially towards the viewpoints of those few individuals who dominate the literature.

Conclusions

In Henderson's view, many of the political challenges to eradication were unforeseeable, and ultimate success required luck as much as careful planning: "Had the effort begun a year earlier or later, it might have failed... In almost every country there were periods when neither surveillance nor eradication programs were possible. The success of these national programs often hung by a thread." [54] Those involved in smallpox eradication disagreed about the right approach – and indeed whether eradication was even feasible – until the very last case [11]. Uniformity of opinion will similarly not be required for malaria eradication to be successful. What is instead required is for national programs and the international institutions that support them to be scientific in their approaches and efficient in their execution – to be open to new tools and strategies, to weigh evidence, revise approaches, and to make data-driven decisions as best they can given imperfect intelligence.

Declarations

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